
The Pé-De-Meia Program as a Public Policy to Encourage Students to Stay in School and Complete High School: Evidence from the First Results

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ABSTRACT: Dropout and evasion in high school are historical challenges in Brazilian education, strongly associated with socioeconomic inequalities that compromise the permanence and completion of this stage by young people in the public school system. In this context, the Pé-de-Meia Program emerges as a public policy of financial incentive aimed at the permanence and completion of high school by public school students in vulnerable situations. This article aims to analyze initial evidence of the implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program in light of selected indicators of school performance, flow, and transition, discussing the extent to which the policy design is compatible with improvements observed in the 2020-2024 period. Methodologically, this is a quantitative, descriptive, and *ex post* study based on secondary data from official databases (Inep, Nilo Peçanha Platform, and Enem statistics), with an emphasis on graphical analysis and the comparison of historical series. The results point to signs of an association between the Program's duration and increased pass rates, reduced dropout and age-grade distortion indicators, and increased participation of public school graduates in Enem, especially among students more exposed to the need for early entry into the labor market. It is concluded that, although still preliminary and subject to important methodological limitations, the findings indicate the relevance of Pé-de-Meia as a policy to support high school retention and completion, highlighting the need for continued monitoring and more robust impact assessments as new data sets and series become available.

KEYWORDS: Public education policies. High school. School dropout. Financial incentives. Pé-de-Meia Program.

1 INTRODUCTION

The universalization of access to primary education in Brazil has not been accompanied, to the same extent, by a guarantee of permanence and completion of secondary education, a stage marked by high rates of dropout, failure, and age-grade distortion, phenomena closely associated with the socioeconomic inequalities that affect school-age youth. Several studies identify the need to work, low family income, and precarious living conditions as the main determinants of school dropout at this stage of basic education, perpetuating cycles of exclusion and limiting trajectories of social mobility.

Recent data from the Continuous National Household Sample Survey (PNAD Contínua), 2nd quarter of 2025 (IBGE, 2025), reveal that around 8.8 million Brazilians between the ages of 15 and 29 did not complete high school and did not attend a basic education institution in 2024. The economic factor is the most relevant determinant for this situation, with almost half of young people pointing to the need to work as the main reason for dropping out, which highlights the difficulty of reconciling study and work in a context of social vulnerability. Also according to the Continuous PNAD (IBGE, 2024, pp. 7-8), the adjusted net school attendance rate – young people aged 15 to 17 attending or having completed high school – reached 76.7% in 2024, an increase of 1.7 percentage points compared to 2023, but remains 8.3 p.p. below the 85% target set by the 2014-2024 National Education Plan (PNE) (Law No. 13,005, of June 25, 2014).

The Report on the 5th Cycle of Monitoring the PNE Goals, released by Inep (2024a, pp. 95-96), summarizes the structural nature of these challenges:

Eight years after the 2016 deadline, universal access to school for young people aged 15 to 17 – underlying Indicator 3A¹ – has not yet been achieved, with 94.0% reaching this indicator in 2023, 6.0 percentage points (p.p.) below the target. Between 2012 and

¹ Indicator 3A: Percentage of the population aged 15 to 17 who attend school or have completed basic education. Target: 100% coverage of this population by 2016 (Brazil, 2014).

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2023, there was a 5.2 p.p. increase in access to school for this age group, but there is still a significant gap to reach the universalization target.

[...] With regard to Indicator 3B², referring to net enrollment rates among young people aged 15 to 17, the results suggest that, in 2023, 76.9% of young people were attending [high school] or had completed basic education, an increase of 13.5 p.p. compared to 2012, but still 8.1 p.p. below the target of 85.0%.

In addition, the most recent data on national school flow indicators for public high schools, for the 2021-2022 cycle, released by Inep in July 2025 (Inep, 2025g), show a repetition rate of 4.6%, dropout rate of 9.5%, and migration to Youth and Adult Education (EJA) of 2.0%, configuring a scenario of persistent difficulty in regular progression.

In this context, socioeconomic inequalities have a disproportionate impact on low-income students, who face limitations in accessing essential resources such as school supplies, transportation, and adequate study conditions, contributing to the perpetuation of the cycle of poverty and transforming education – which could be a vector for social mobility – into an additional barrier to inclusion (Madaloz *et al.*, 2024). Public educational policies offering conditional financial incentives have been consolidated, both nationally and internationally, as strategies to mitigate these effects, acting on the economic determinants of dropout and promoting qualified retention.

The Pé-de-Meia Program, established by Law No. 14,818/2024 and regulated by Decree No. 11,901/2024, is part of this set of initiatives, creating an innovative educational savings mechanism conditional on enrollment, minimum attendance of 80% of class hours, annual approval, and participation in the National High School Exam (Enem), with benefits totaling up to R\$ 9,200 per eligible student. The policy transcends mere income transfer by establishing explicit strategic objectives to reduce retention, dropout, and truancy rates (Art. 2, item III), mitigate social inequalities, and encourage the transition to higher and technical education, breaking the intergenerational cycle of poverty (Brazil, 2024a; Brazil, 2024b).

According to data from the Federal Government's Transparency Portal³, in its first year of implementation (2024), the Program reached R\$ 9.2 billion in expenditures, benefiting 4.1 million students. Coverage reached about 60% of public high school enrollments, according to data from the 2024 School Census (Inep, 2025a), with high relevance for the Federal EPCT Network⁴, whose socioeconomic quota profile reinforces its priority eligibility (Law No. 12,711/2012).

According to Pereira (2016, p. 77), the central innovation of the design lies in the creation of a financial reward for students to combat the temporal myopia typical of adolescence, in which the immediate opportunity cost of work often outweighs the future benefits of education, bringing immediate decision horizons closer to long-term educational returns.

The literature from neuroscience shows that adolescence is a period of intense structural change in the brain (Spear, 2000). The maturation changes in the brain during adolescence contribute to some of the behavioral differences from adolescence to other ages, such as a higher predisposition to take risky attitudes and a tendency to focus on the present and ignore future consequences. In the presence of this myopic behavior, financial rewards for high school graduation can effectively decrease dropout rates.

In this sense, formulating a public policy that minimizes this scenario requires initiative and interest from the public sector in contributing to the improvement of the conditions of the most vulnerable, as well as the success of its contribution to the retention of these students. Given this perspective, it is necessary to understand how the new policy has been instrumental in reducing dropout rates and increasing high school completion rates among socially vulnerable young people in its first year of implementation.

Thus, this article analyzes the initial results of the Program as a public education policy, verifying the extent to which its initial objectives are reflected in the indicators of school flow, performance, and transition observed in the 2020-2024 historical series, with the hypothesis that the financial incentive acts as a determining factor for the retention and completion of high school among vulnerable students in the public school system. The success of the initiative will be measured precisely by its ability to consistently change academic performance indicators in the next census cycles, with a more evident impact on the groups historically most affected by school exclusion.

The article is organized into five main sections. After this introduction, the theoretical framework discusses school dropout, the architecture of financial incentives, and *ex post* evaluation of public policies. The methodology section details the quantitative-descriptive design, secondary data sources (Inep, Nilo Peçanha Platform, Enem), and analytical limitations. The analysis of results and discussion presents the evolution of indicators of enrollment, approval, age-grade distortion, dropout, academic efficiency, and participation in Enem, comparing them to the Program's objectives. Finally, the conclusion summarizes the preliminary findings, their implications for public education policies, and recommendations for future monitoring.

² Indicator 3B: Percentage of the population aged 15 to 17 who attend secondary school or have completed basic education. Target: Achieve 85% net enrollment in secondary education by 2024 (Brazil, 2014).

³ <https://portaldatransparencia.gov.br/beneficios?ano=2024>

⁴ Federal Network for Professional, Scientific, and Technological Education.

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2 THEORETICAL REFERENCE

2.1 SCHOOL DROPOUT AND FINANCIAL INCENTIVES

The National Education Guidelines and Framework Law (LDB) (Law No. 9,394, of December 20, 1996) defines the recommended ages for each stage of basic education, which is compulsory from ages 4 to 17. For high school, the ideal age range is between 15 and 17 years old (Brazil, 1996). Understanding the presence and absence of young people in this cycle is an essential step in diagnosing school exclusion and planning educational policies aimed at retention. The estimate of the population of young people aged 15 to 17 who are out of school is based on the Continuous National Household Sample Survey (PNAD Contínua), conducted by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), the main source of up-to-date information on the educational and socioeconomic conditions of the Brazilian population.

School dropout in Brazilian high schools is a multi-causal phenomenon, situated at the intersection of socioeconomic conditions, school trajectories marked by failure and age-grade distortion, and subjective dimensions linked to the meaning of schooling for young people. Recent studies indicate that socioeconomic inequalities affect low-income students more intensely, whose access to basic resources – such as teaching materials, transportation, and minimum study conditions – is often limited, contributing to the intergenerational reproduction of poverty and often transforming school from a potential instrument of social mobility into yet another barrier to inclusion. In this scenario, the need for early entry into the labor market repeatedly appears as a central reason for dropping out, especially among young people aged 14 to 29.

According to Branco *et al.* (2020), dropout rates tend to increase as the level of education advances, driven by external factors (such as economic pressure and the need to contribute to family income) and internal factors (such as the disconnect between the school curriculum and students' life plans). Similarly, Madaloz *et al.* (2024) emphasize that the absence of financial incentives is a determining factor for low-income students leaving school, highlighting that the lack of financial incentives negatively impacts student retention, alongside barriers to access such as poor transportation and a lack of resources to cover the costs of school life.

The international literature on the economics of education also highlights that adolescents tend to underestimate or “overdiscount” the future benefits of education, favoring immediate gains over long-term returns, such as completing high school. Pereira (2016, p. 63), in analyzing the Renda Melhor Jovem program in Rio de Janeiro, shows that despite the “substantial gains associated with high school completion,” dropout rates remain high, which has led many economists to suggest that young people “ignore or greatly discount the benefits of completing high school,” in line with evidence from neurology and psychology that characterizes adolescence as a period particularly prone to short-sighted behavior.

In this context, conditional financial incentive policies are designed as mechanisms to correct this “temporal myopia,” bringing the benefits perceived by students closer to the short-term decision horizon. Pereira (2016, p. 76) documents evidence that a performance bonus deposited in a linked account, with full withdrawal only at the end of high school, combined with penalties in case of failure or dropout, produces statistically significant effects in raising pass rates and reducing dropout rates among adolescents in extreme poverty.

This paper presents evidence that attainment awards that pay poor high school students for graduating from high school can substantially reduce dropout and increase high school graduation rates among economically disadvantaged youths. The program design exploits students' loss aversion by paying for each grade passed, but by locking the amount transferred in a bank account, and only releasing the full amount to the student after timely graduation from high school. This rule possibly creates a strong incentive for students who are loss averse, and is likely to influence students who highly discount the future or who present myopic behavior. In our preferred specification, being eligible to receive the incentive award decreases dropout rates by roughly 37%, and increases grade passing rates by 14%.

Results from recent research on the Pé-de-Meia Program, although still in its early stages, partially converge in this direction: case studies indicate that the benefit works for some students as a direct incentive to stay in school, while for others it is primarily used to cover basic needs, revealing both its potential and its limitations in addressing the problem of dropout rates on its own.

Thus, the theoretical debate on school dropout and financial incentives points, on the one hand, to the relevance of monetary instruments aimed at vulnerable young people and, on the other, to the need to understand them as components of broader strategies to combat educational inequalities, linked to pedagogical policies, social protection, and the improvement of school conditions.

Analyzing international experience and in light of the Brazilian reality, Haddad *et al.* (2022, p. 6) established recommendations to increase the chance of effectiveness of financial incentive policies for high school completion, including:

The program should not be seen as the ultimate solution to the problems of Brazilian high school education. Most of the articles analyzed point to the beneficial effects of financial incentives for students in terms of schooling. However, although significant, the magnitude of the effects is not sufficient to solve, as a whole, the serious educational problem in Brazil. This conclusion applies to all variables analyzed: flow, dropout, completion, and access to higher education, among others. For example, in Brazil, the net enrollment rate in high school is only 75% for young people between the ages of 15 and 17. The greatest effects found in the literature on financial aid programs on enrollment rates range from 3 to 5 percentage points.

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2.2. INCENTIVE ARCHITECTURE AND CONDITIONALITIES: LAW No. 14,818/2024

The implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program, as established by Law No. 14,818/2024 and regulated by Decree No. 11,901/2024, is structured around four interrelated types of financial and educational incentives. This architecture was designed to simultaneously alleviate immediate economic constraints and build long-term savings, conditioning receipt on the fulfillment of academic and social requirements. From an analytical perspective, the program's design is similar to international experiences of awards for performance or timely completion of high school, such as Renda Melhor Jovem, which combine deposits into a linked account, partial access to funds during the course, and severe penalties in case of failure or dropout, exploiting both positive incentives and students' aversion to loss (Pereira, 2016).

To be eligible for the program, students must be between 14 and 24 years old, belong to a low-income family registered in the Single Registry for Social Programs (CadÚnico), and be enrolled in public high school (federal, state, district, or municipal). The legislation provides for the granting of the following benefits, totaling up to R\$ 9,200 per eligible student, until the completion of public high school:

- a) Enrollment Incentive: a single annual amount of R\$ 200, paid for enrollment registered at the beginning of each school year;
- b) Attendance Incentive: a monthly amount of R\$ 200, paid in nine (9) installments throughout the year, totaling R\$ 1,800, conditional on proof of minimum school attendance of 80% of monthly class hours, a level higher than the minimum of 75% provided for in the Law of Guidelines and Bases for National Education (LDB) for regular approval;
- c) Completion Incentive: annual amount of R\$ 1,000, deposited at the end of each school year completed with approval, accumulating up to R\$ 3,000, with withdrawal allowed only at the end of high school;
- d) Enem Incentive: a single amount of R\$ 200 for third-year public high school students who register and participate in the two days of Enem exams, under the terms of Decree No. 11,901/2024 and MEC Ordinance No. 470/2025 (Brazil, 2024b; Brazil, 2025a).

It is important to highlight the hybrid nature of the availability of these resources. While the Enrollment Incentive and the Attendance Incentive can be accessed monthly by students, mitigating the need for immediate work and material barriers to school access, the Completion Incentive is a blocked educational savings account, which can only be fully withdrawn after the certified completion of all high school education. This combination is similar to the mechanism described by Pereira (2016), in which the accumulated balance can only be fully withdrawn at the end of the cycle, and the student simultaneously experiences the prospect of future gain and the risk of loss in case of dropout or failure.

Recent studies on Pé-de-Meia emphasize that this structure of benefits and conditions reinforces the objective of not only guaranteeing access, but also ensuring qualified permanence and completion of basic education, directly combating dropout motivated by economic factors and mitigating inequalities of opportunity among students from different social backgrounds. Madaloz *et al.* (2024) define the Program as "a proactive and structured measure to strengthen the Brazilian educational system" by directing resources specifically to students in vulnerable situations, with a view to promoting financial inclusion and equal opportunities in completing high school.

Finally, according to Article 5, item III, of Decree No. 11,901/2024, students may be removed from the Program in case of dropout, abandonment, or failure twice in a row or for a period of two years, which gives the institutional arrangement an additional disciplinary component and reinforces the commitment to academic success. This logic is in line with the literature on conditional transfer programs, according to which the careful definition of what is encouraged, how the incentive is framed, and the sanctions associated with non-compliance with the conditions is decisive for maximizing the effectiveness and cost-benefit ratio of the policy (Pereira, 2016, p. 65).

Choosing the right incentive (Barrera-Osorio *et al.*, 2011), how to frame the incentive (Barrera-Osorio and Filmer, 2013) or how to label it (Benhassine *et al.*, 2015) has important consequences over the magnitude of the program impact. Correctly targeting and designing the incentive portion of CCT [conditional cash transfers] programs is crucial in order to maximize its cost effectiveness.

2.3. PUBLIC POLICY EVALUATION: THE *EX POST* PERSPECTIVE

The evaluation of public policies occupies a central place in the contemporary agenda of state management, constituting a fundamental instrument for assessing the efficiency (use of resources), efficacy (achievement of goals), and effectiveness (social impacts) of government interventions. According to the Practical Guide to *Ex Post* Analysis of the Civil House, evaluation after implementation allows not only to verify whether the objectives have been achieved, but also to identify design and execution flaws, guide adjustments and improvements, and support decisions on the continuity, expansion, or redirection of policies (Brazil, 2018a). In the specific field of educational policies, Haddad *et al.* (2022) emphasize that "all public policies must be evaluated *ex post* to ensure that their objectives have been achieved," stressing that evaluation is important "also for adjustments to the program design in order to make it increasingly efficient in accordance with the objectives set," and may even identify "spillover effects on actors who are not the focus of the programs but who have the potential to generate desired and positive results" (Haddad *et al.*, 2022, p.

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8). This perspective is particularly relevant for financial incentive programs for students, whose impact depends both on the individual response of beneficiaries and on broader changes in school and family dynamics.

In the case of the Pé-de-Meia Program, the *ex post* perspective involves monitoring whether the policy design – based on payments conditional on enrollment, attendance, completion, and participation in the Enem – translates into consistent improvements in indicators of retention, performance, and educational transition, explicitly considering its temporal and methodological limitations. As this is a high-cost policy that has only recently been implemented, the consolidation of a robust monitoring and evaluation system, with clear goals and defined indicators, is essential both to inform the public debate on its merits and to ensure the best use of available resources.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DESIGN AND NATURE OF THE RESEARCH

This research is characterized as a quantitative, descriptive, and exploratory study, with an *ex post* design for the evaluation of public policies, focused on the analysis of secondary indicators of school performance, flow, and transition in the historical series 2020-2024. The methodological focus is on verifying variations and trends in academic indicators in the first year of implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program (2024), assuming an observational character suitable for identifying preliminary signs of alignment between empirical results and the normative objectives of the policy, recognizing the impossibility of causal inference in such a restricted time horizon (Brazil, 2018a).

3.2 DATA SOURCES

The data come from official educational statistics databases:

- a) Annual Statistical Synopses of Basic Education and Educational Indicators from Inep, covering enrollment, public high school graduates, school performance rates (pass, fail, dropout), and age-grade distortion at the national level (Inep, 2025a; Inep, 2025b);
- b) ENEM Statistical Synopses and Microdata, with figures on public high school graduates enrolled and present on the two days of testing (Inep, 2025c; Inep, 2025d); and
- c) Nilo Peçanha Platform (PNP), the official statistics environment of the Federal EPCT Network established by Setec/MEC Ordinance No. 1/2018, which provides management indicators such as Dropout Rate, Academic Efficiency Index, and Retention Index by Cycle (Brazil, 2018b; Brazil, 2021; Brazil, 2025b).

Inep defines enrollment as formal registration in the Educacenso System on the Census reference date (last Wednesday in May) (Inep, 2024b), while the PNP considers those who remained actively enrolled for at least one day during the year to be enrolled, according to the Methodological Reference Guide for Educational Statistics of the Federal Network (Brazil, 2020; Brazil, 2021). The series analyzed (2020-2024) contextualizes the implementation milestone of Pé-de-Meia, with the caveat that the evidence for 2024 is preliminary.

3.3 ANALYTICAL STRATEGY

The analysis adopts descriptive and comparative procedures:

- a) Analysis of time series with absolute and relative variations (percentage points) between consecutive years and over the total period;
- b) Identification of trends and inflections correlated in time with the implementation of the Program;
- c) Comparison between aggregate levels (national vs. Federal Network) to highlight institutional singularities; and
- d) Exploratory interpretation aligning observed variations with the mechanisms of the Pé-de-Meia program, recognizing alternative factors such as post-COVID-19 recovery and complementary policies (Haddad *et al.*, 2022).

3.4 INDICATORS ANALYSED

The main educational indicators of efficiency and academic performance analyzed in this article, listed below, are defined in the Inep Dictionary of Educational Indicators (Inep, 2004) and in the Methodological Reference Guide for Educational Statistics of the Federal Network (Brazil, 2020):

- a) Pass Rate: percentage of students who pass out of those enrolled (Inep, 2025e);
- b) Failure rate: percentage of students who failed out of those enrolled (Inep, 2025e);
- c) Dropout rate: percentage of students who dropped out of school in any grade before the end of the school year (Instituto Unibanco, 2024; Inep, 2025e);
- d) Age-Grade Distortion Rate (AGDR): percentage of students who are two or more years behind in school, according to Inep methodology (Unicef, 2018; Inep, 2025f);

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- e) Dropout Rate: percentage of students who dropped out of school before completing a course or stage of education, not renewing their enrollment in the following school year, even though they had passed or failed the previous one, resulting in the definitive interruption of their studies (Instituto Unibanco, 2024; Inep, 2025g);
- f) Retention Rate per Cycle: specific to the Federal EPCT Network, percentage of enrolled students exceeding the course completion deadline (+1 year) (Brazil, 2025b);
- g) Academic Efficiency Index: specific to the Federal EPCT Network, percentage of graduates within the expected period (+1 year), plus a percentage (projection) of students retained in the reference year who may complete the course (Brazil, 2025b); and
- h) Enem Participation Rate of Graduates: percentage of graduates enrolled in Enem in relation to the total number of students enrolled in the third year of high school registered in the School Census (Inep, 2025a; Inep, 2025c; Inep, 2025d), also considering studies that address student participation in Enem (Silva; Rosistolato, 2021).

3.5 METHODOLOGICAL LIMITATIONS

This study acknowledges the following limitations:

- a) Lack of granular disaggregation: the data used are aggregated at the national and Federal Network levels, not allowing for differentiated analysis by school unit, municipality, or individual student characteristics;
- b) Lack of control of confounding variables: the analysis does not apply matching, stratification, or statistical modeling techniques to isolate the specific effect of the Pé-de-Meia Program from other factors that also influence educational indicators;
- c) Limited time horizon: only one year of full implementation (2024) is available for analysis, which is insufficient to establish sustained effects or identify cyclical patterns;
- d) Impossibility of causal inference: the variations observed in the indicators cannot be attributed exclusively to the Program and should be interpreted as signs of temporal association and compatibility with policy objectives;
- e) Influence of alternative factors: the 2020-2024 series covers a critical period of post-pandemic recovery from COVID-19, during which multiple federal and state education policies were implemented, making it difficult to isolate specific effects.

Although the research is based on official and methodologically robust data, the interval of approximately three years between the reference year and the release of longitudinal indicators at the national level limits the ability to assess, in a timely manner, the adherence of empirical results to the normative and objectives established by Law No. 14,818/2024, especially with regard to the reduction of retention, repetition, and school dropout rates, whose results for the 2024-2025 cycle, covering the first year of Pé-de-Meia's implementation, are expected to be released by Inep in mid-2028. In this sense, the time limitation on the availability of national school flow indicators introduces an important structural bias in the analyses developed in this study, since the effects of the Pé-de-Meia Program on central variables such as dropout and repetition cannot be observed in the same time frame in which the policy is implemented.

In this sense, the evaluation of the Program at the national level in this article is based predominantly on short-term outcome indicators – such as pass rates and age-grade distortion – which, although relevant, do not fully capture the dynamics of transition between grades and stages, nor do they allow for the identification of interrupted trajectories over time. This limitation implies that the conclusions presented here are necessarily preliminary, aimed at identifying trends and initial signs of alignment with the policy's objectives, rather than exhaustively measuring its effectiveness on school flow in the strict sense.

Additionally, the delay in the dissemination of longitudinal indicators reduces the ability of public managers, researchers, and social control bodies to carry out monitoring and reassessments in a timely manner, which, as a result, delays the adoption of course adjustments and the correction of possible distortions in the implementation of the Program. In this context, the analysis developed in this study should be understood as an analytical snapshot conditioned by the limitations of the national statistical production system, which reinforces the need for caution in extrapolating findings and formulating inferences about the medium- and long-term impact of Pé-de-Meia on school flow indicators.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This section presents and discusses the results related to the main indicators of school performance and flow, with an emphasis on the comparison between the period immediately prior to the implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program and the first year of its implementation. The analysis seeks to identify trends and possible signs of alignment between the behavior of the indicators and the policy objectives, subject to the methodological limitations already explained. The results of the indicators come from publicly available national- y data on enrollment, school performance rates (pass, fail, and dropout), and age-grade distortion rates, released by the Anísio Teixeira National Institute for Educational Studies and Research (Inep), an agency linked to the Ministry of Education, as well as on school flow/transition rates (dropout) and retention rates by cycle and academic efficiency in federal public high schools extracted from the Nilo Peçanha Platform (PNP).

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4.1. ENROLLMENT AND SCHOOL PERFORMANCE RATES IN PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOLS

Graph 1 shows that total enrollment in public secondary education (1st to 3rd grade) remained relatively stable in the 2020-2024 period, fluctuating between 6.75 and 6.90 million students, with no abrupt changes in coverage. This stability in enrollment numbers indicates that any changes in performance indicators are mainly due to internal dynamics of school flow, rather than significant movements in expansion or contraction of access.

Graph 1 - Number of public school enrollments in high school⁵ in Brazil and respective School Performance Rates (2020 to 2024)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the annual Statistical Synopses of Basic Education and Educational Indicators related to School Performance Rates.

With regard to performance rates, a more volatile behavior can be observed, especially in the years immediately following the Covid-19 pandemic. In 2022, the worst performance in the series is recorded, with the pass rate falling to 85.1%, accompanied by a significant increase in failure (8.4%) and dropout (6.5%), suggesting a scenario of severe disruption to school trajectories. From 2023 onwards, however, there is a gradual recovery in these indicators: pass rates return to levels above 90% (90.5% in 2023 and 90.9% in 2024), while failure and dropout rates fall to levels below those observed at the height of the crisis (5.6% and 3.5%, respectively, in 2024).

In the context of the first year of implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program (2024), this improvement in school performance is consistent with the objectives of the policy, which seeks to reduce failure and dropout rates through financial incentives conditional on enrollment, attendance, and completion. Although it is not possible to attribute direct causality, the maintenance of high pass rates, associated with a reduction in failure and dropout rates in a scenario of stable enrollment, suggests an environment more favorable to remaining in and completing high school, especially among students in situations of socioeconomic vulnerability.

4.2. AGE-GRADE DISPARITY RATE IN HIGH SCHOOL

Graph 2 shows the evolution of the age-grade distortion rate (AGDR) in high school in Brazil, broken down by school system (public, private, and total) for the period 2020-2024. The results point to a consistent trajectory of reduction in distortion in the public system, from 28.9% in 2020 to 19.7% in 2024, indicating a drop of more than 9 percentage points over the historical series. A similar trend, albeit at a lower level, is observed in the private system, with the total indicator also showing a continuous decline over the period.

⁵ The total for secondary education includes enrollment in regular preparatory secondary education, integrated technical courses (integrated secondary education), and normal/teaching secondary education.

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Graph 2 - Age-Grade Distortion Rate in Secondary Education in Brazil by education network (2020 to 2024)

Source: Own elaboration based on Educational Indicators related to Age-Grade Distortion Rates.

From an analytical point of view, these results show a double movement: on the one hand, the progressive correction of accumulated school delays, with a lower proportion of students attending grades incompatible with their expected age; on the other hand, the persistence of significant asymmetries between networks, which reflect structural inequalities in supply, teaching conditions, and the socioeconomic profile of the student body. The combination of a reduction in age-grade distortion and an improvement in pass rates observed in 2023 and 2024 suggests a more favorable environment for the regularization of school flow, even though part of this improvement stems from policies and efforts prior to the creation of the Pé-de-Meia Program.

It is also important to note that the reduction in age-grade distortion in the public school system observed in the 2020-2024 period, although consistent, does not eliminate the gap in relation to the private school system, which shows that financial incentives alone are insufficient to equalize school trajectory patterns between such unequal socioeconomic contexts. The literature on financial incentive policies indicates positive effects, albeit of moderate magnitude, which reinforces the need to combine programs such as Pé-de-Meia with structural measures to improve the quality of provision, curriculum organization, and learning conditions, lest we only partially reduce a problem that is both a symptom and a cause of broader educational inequalities.

Graph 3 shows the evolution of the age-grade distortion rate in Brazilian public high schools, broken down by grade (1st, 2nd, and 3rd grades) for the period 2020-2024, revealing distinct patterns of school delay throughout high school. It can be observed that the distortion is more pronounced in the 1st grade in all the years analyzed, with values consistently higher than those of subsequent grades, suggesting that late entry or initial repetition accumulate effects that are perpetuated throughout the cycle. In the historical series, all three grades show a downward trend in distortion, albeit with different intensities and rates, indicating a progressive correction of school flow in the public school system.

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Graph 3 - Age-grade distortion rate by grade in public high schools in Brazil (2020 to 2024)

Source: Own elaboration based on Educational Indicators related to Age-Grade Distortion Rates.

Analytically, the results show that age-grade distortion is not evenly distributed throughout high school, but is concentrated mainly at the beginning of the cycle (1st grade), where the highest values signal problems of late access, accumulated repetition in elementary school, or migration from other educational systems. The reduction observed in all grades, especially between 2022 and 2024, suggests that school regularization policies – including continuous progression, parallel recovery, and incentives for permanence – have generated cumulative positive effects on the flow, with a lower proportion of students attending grades incompatible with their expected age (15-16 years for 1st grade, 16-17 for 2nd grade, and 17-18 for 3rd grade).

By the end of the first year of implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program (2024), this downward trajectory will take on strategic relevance, since the indicator is recognized in the literature as an important predictor of future dropout: students who accumulate repetitions and are “out of age” tend to drop out of school more frequently, especially when pressured by economic needs. By mitigating the urgency of early entry into the labor market and creating financial incentives associated with staying in and completing high school, the Program acts precisely on one of the mechanisms that fuel the distortion, even though the data available until 2024 only allow us to identify compatibility between the policy design and the observed trend, and not to attribute the inflection of the indicator exclusively to it.

However, there are still significant asymmetries between the grades that require specific attention. The persistently higher distortion in the 1st grade points to bottlenecks at the time of entry into high school, possibly associated with the transition from elementary school, while the relative convergence between the 2nd and 3rd grades indicates that retention policies are more effective in the middle and final stages of the cycle. This heterogeneity reinforces that financial incentives such as Pé-de-Meia, although relevant to mitigate economic pressures on vulnerable students (especially in the 3rd grade, close to the age limit for eligibility), are insufficient on their own to equalize trajectories marked by structural inequalities in access and quality.

The literature on educational policy evaluation emphasizes that reductions in age-grade distortion, although positive, should be interpreted with caution in the short term, as they may reflect both real improvements in flow and composition effects (fewer students with severe learning deficits entering the system). In the case of Pé-de-Meia, the 2024 data only allow us to identify preliminary signs of alignment with its objectives of reducing retention and dropout rates (Art. 2, item III, Law No. 14,818/2024), requiring future longitudinal analyses to verify whether the decline in distortion is sustained and associated with higher rates of effective completion of high school in the public school system.

4.3. DROPOUT RATES AND RETENTION INDICES BY CYCLE AND ACADEMIC EFFICIENCY IN FEDERAL PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOLS

Graph 4 summarizes the evolution of the number of enrollments in high school in the Federal Network of Professional, Scientific, and Technological Education, as well as the dropout rate, the Academic Efficiency Index, and the Retention Index by Cycle, for the period 2020-2024. There has been a significant increase in enrollment, from 0.98 million in 2020 to 1.37 million in 2024, suggesting an expansion in the number of places available and the presence of the Federal Network in secondary education.

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Graph 4 - Number of enrollments in secondary education in the Federal Public Network/PNP⁶ and respective results of academic performance indicators (2020 to 2024)

Source: Own elaboration based on data extracted from the Nilo Peçanha Platform.

From a flow perspective, it can be seen that the dropout rate, although still high in some years, shows a downward trend at the end of the series, while the Academic Efficiency Index rises, indicating a higher proportion of students completing courses within the expected time (or with a slight delay) and greater use of the educational effort. At the same time, the Retention Index per Cycle tends to decrease, which signals a reduction in the number of students who exceed the completion period excessively, contributing to a more regular and efficient flow.

In the context of the implementation of the Pé-de-Meia Program, these results suggest that the Federal Network – already characterized by performance indicators above the national average – has favorable institutional conditions to enhance the effects of financial incentives on student retention and academic success. The combination of enrollment expansion, reduced dropout rates, increased academic efficiency, and decreased prolonged retention is consistent with the Program's strategic objectives and indicates an environment in which policy can reinforce trajectories of academic success, especially among low-income students who enter the Federal Network through inclusive access policies, such as the Quota Law (Law No. 12,711/2012).

However, it is necessary to recognize that these improvements stem from a broad set of factors, including investments in infrastructure, specific pedagogical policies, and the selective profile of the Federal Network itself, which prevents the direct attribution of results to Pé-de-Meia. Nevertheless, a careful reading of the indicators reinforces the hypothesis that financial incentive programs, when combined with high-quality institutional environments, tend to generate positive synergies in reducing dropout rates and optimizing school flow.

4.4. PARTICIPATION RATE IN THE ENEM OF PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOL GRADUATES

Graph 5 shows the evolution of the number of public high school graduates (federal, state, and municipal), specifically those enrolled in the third year, as well as the enrollment and effective participation rates (attendance on both days of the exam) in the ENEM, for the period 2020-2024. In absolute terms, the total number of graduates enrolled in the Enem fluctuates between 0.69 and 0.84 million, without abrupt variations, while the number of graduates enrolled and present on the two days of the Enem exams grows more pronouncedly throughout the series.

⁶ Filters in the PNP: [Type of Course] = Professional Qualification (FIC), High School, Technical; [Type of Offer] = Not applicable, Concurrent, Integrated.

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Graph 5 - Number of public high school seniors in Brazil and respective Enem registration and participation rates⁷ (2020 to 2024)

Source: Prepared by the authors based on the annual Statistical Synopses of Basic Education; annual Statistical Synopses of the Enem; and Enem microdata.

The rates derived from these figures reveal two relevant trends. First, the proportion of public school graduates enrolled in the Enem increases from 38.5% in 2020 to 43.1% in 2024, indicating that a growing fraction of graduates seek the exam as a gateway to higher education. Second, the attendance rate among enrolled graduates – that is, the proportion of those who actually attend the two days of testing – rises from 52.71% in 2020 to 70.16% in 2024, suggesting greater engagement and commitment to taking the exam.

These results are particularly significant in light of the design of the Pé-de-Meia Program, which establishes the Enem Incentive as a specific benefit conditional on registration and participation in both days of the exam. The simultaneous increase in registration and attendance rates among public school graduates is consistent with the goal of encouraging the transition from basic education to higher education, reducing material and symbolic barriers for low-income students to participate in the main university entrance exam.

Although the trend toward recovery in Enem participation is already evident after the most critical period of the pandemic, the level observed in 2024 suggests that the financial incentive may be contributing to consolidating this recovery, increasing exam participation precisely among groups that have historically been underrepresented in higher education. Nevertheless, given the short time frame and the existence of other competing factors (such as fee exemption policies, mobilization campaigns, and changes to the exam itself), the analysis should be interpreted as preliminary evidence of alignment between the behavior of graduates and the program's objectives, rather than definitive proof of its impact on participation rates.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The results analyzed in this article indicate that the Pé-de-Meia Program has significant potential as a public policy to encourage high school retention and completion, especially among public school students in situations of socioeconomic vulnerability. Initial evidence suggests a positive correlation between the granting of financial-educational incentives and improved performance indicators, such as passing rates, reduced dropout rates, and increased participation in the National High School Exam (ENEM), although these findings should be interpreted as associations compatible with the policy's objectives, rather than as conclusive evidence of causal impact.

⁷ To calculate the variable “Total number of public high school graduates enrolled in Enem and present on both days of the exam,” the following filters were used in the Enem microdata: [TP_ST_CONCLUSAO] = 2; [TP_DEPENDENCIA_ADM_ESC] = 1, 2, and 3; [TP_PRESENCA_CN] = 1; [TP_PRESENCA_CH] = 1; [TP_PRESENCA_LC] = 1; and [TP_PRESENCA_MT] = 1. For the year 2024, due to changes in the Enem Microdata model made by INEP, data on this variable were obtained through a request for access to information on the Fala.BR Platform.

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However, it should be noted that the six formal objectives of the Program are broad and ambitious, ranging from reducing dropout and retention rates to mitigating social inequalities and encouraging students to continue their studies in higher and technical education. In light of this multiplicity of purposes, it is unlikely that a single policy instrument – centered on financial incentives – will be able, on its own, to produce profound changes in all these dimensions, especially in a time frame as short as the first year of implementation. This finding reinforces the need to situate Pé-de-Meia as part of a broader policy arrangement for secondary education, rather than as a self-sufficient solution to the historical problems of this stage.

From an evaluative standpoint, it should also be noted that the policy lacks clear operational goals and an explicit set of key indicators to be monitored, which makes it difficult to establish objective criteria for assessing its effectiveness. Unlike other recent federal initiatives, such as the National Commitment to Child Literacy and the Full-Time School Program, which announce specific quantitative coverage and performance targets within a defined time frame, Pé-de-Meia does not specify, for example, what reduction in dropout or truancy rates it expects to achieve in three or five years, nor what equity targets should guide its implementation. This lack of measurable goals weakens the *ex post* evaluation of the policy and makes it more difficult to account to society for the use of the resources involved.

This point is particularly sensitive because it is a high-cost policy, with estimated annual expenditure in the billions of reais, an amount higher than that of other structural programs recently implemented in the Brazilian educational agenda. In contexts of budgetary constraints, the literature on public policy evaluation emphasizes the importance of comparing relative costs and benefits between programs, identifying whether the resources employed could generate greater impact in alternative or complementary arrangements. Thus, it is essential that Pé-de-Meia be subject to frequent evaluations, using more robust methods and longer historical series, capable of estimating with greater precision the magnitude of its effects on school flow, educational inequalities, and transition to higher education, in order to understand its impacts and make any improvements and adjustments to its design.

Even when international and national studies point to the positive effects of financial incentive policies for young people, the magnitude of these impacts is usually moderate – often in the order of a few percentage points in indicators such as enrollment, attendance, or completion – which falls short of the structural transformation required by the current state of Brazilian secondary education. In a scenario where the net enrollment rate still remains below the desired level and profound inequalities in access, retention, and learning persist, a financial support program tends to function as an important piece within a more complex “mechanism,” but not as a single or sufficient solution to reverse the situation of exclusion and school failure on its own.

The findings of this study, while showing promising signs of alignment between the program's design and the evolution of some indicators, they also reinforce the centrality of integrated policies that combine monetary incentives with pedagogical strategies, psychosocial support actions, improvement of teaching conditions, improvement of governance and financing of secondary education, expansion of professional and technological education, and extension of the school day, among other fronts. If schools do not become more attractive, welcoming, and connected to young people's life projects, infrequent attendance, dropouts, and truancy are likely to remain structural challenges, even if they can be partially reduced by transfer or educational savings programs. It can therefore be concluded that the Pé-de-Meia Program constitutes an important advance in the agenda of equity and social justice in education, by explicitly recognizing the weight of economic constraints on the educational trajectory of vulnerable young people and seeking to address them through financial and educational incentives. However, in order for its potential to be fully realized, it will be necessary to: (i) specify medium- and long-term goals and outcome indicators; (ii) institutionalize a system of continuous monitoring and evaluation, with a focus on cost-effectiveness; and (iii) link the program to a broader set of reforms and structural policies for secondary education. In this sense, Pé-de-Meia should be understood less as a definitive solution and more as a strategic component of a systemic project to reconfigure the stage, whose effectiveness will depend on the quality of its coordination with other initiatives and the rigor with which it is monitored and improved over time.

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